

MERGE

MEASURING WHAT MATTERS

Policy pathways to sustainable and
inclusive wellbeing

Deliverable 4.2

Policy Brief: Public support for Beyond GDP indicators and policy frameworks in the European Union

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About

The MERGE project, titled "Measuring What Matters: Improving Usability and Accessibility of Policy Frameworks and Indicators for Multidimensional Wellbeing through Collaboration" is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by Horizon Europe under contract No. 101132524. The project seeks to explore pathways toward inclusive and sustainable wellbeing.

With 16 partners, MERGE builds on the scientific work of other Horizon Europe consortiums, including WISE Horizons, ToBe, and SPES, as well as the European Research Council-funded project REAL. These initiatives contribute valuable knowledge on alternative indicators beyond GDP, sustainable policy options, and scenarios for a more sustainable future.

MERGE aims to create synergies between these projects, fostering a strong, science-based forum for advancing beyond GDP policies and indicators. This report presents the perspectives of MERGE stakeholders on beyond GDP metrics and concepts, contributing to the broader beyond GDP agenda.

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Document History

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Brief Description	This brief presents the findings of a cross-country survey data collected by MERGE in October-November 2024. The online survey was administered to nationally representative samples of six European Union countries: Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland and Spain. A total of 6,000 participants gave their opinion on the adoption and use of Beyond GDP indicators in policy making. Through participant's responses to our questions, we learnt about the topics and dimensions that they feel these indicators should focus on; as well as their views for a sustainable Europe by 2050. The questionnaire included a survey experiment which tested the effectiveness of different communication strategies on public support for Beyond GDP indicators.
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Executive Summary

The transition to Beyond GDP (BGDP) metrics represents a pivotal shift from traditional economic indicators to a more holistic approach to measuring societal progress. We find that with over 80% of European citizens supporting the adoption of BGDP measures to guide national performance and policy objectives, there is a clear public demand for indicators that prioritize wellbeing, sustainability, and inclusivity. However, the successful integration of BGDP metrics requires the alignment with public sentiment and effective communication.

Despite widespread support for BGDP measures, the acceptance of such indicators varies across demographic groups. For instance, younger people, women, and those dissatisfied with their lives show greater support, while older individuals, higher-income groups, and those with conservative views tend to be less favourable. To address these variations, targeted communication strategies could be helpful. For example, while highlighting equality and inclusion might appeal to the majority of Europeans, we find that this approach could be counterproductive with the higher educated. In addition, emphasizing the improvement in quality of life that moving Beyond GDP could bring about, would be more effective in increasing support among higher-income individuals.

One important finding is the robust support for measuring societal progress through a combination of indicators measuring wellbeing, sustainability, and inclusion. Approximately 60% of respondents support a broad set of BGDP indicators that capture all three dimensions. This preference aligns with the notion that policies must address both the immediate needs of current generations and the long-term wellbeing of future generations, whilst ensuring that wellbeing is distributed fairly across society. Public support for BGDP metrics is highest, especially for indicators that address topics such as health, safety, jobs, education, and housing.

The European public' aspirations when it comes to sustainable visions for Europe in 2050 crucially depend on their pre-existing beliefs regarding the plausibility of alternative scenarios. These beliefs relate to their views on whether absolute decoupling of economic activity from emissions is possible, but also to their perceptions regarding the role of GDP in steering policymaking. Ensuring that these expectations are realistic, and that the public possesses a base knowledge on alternatives to GDP can help ensure its support towards a greater adoption and integration of Beyond GDP indicators into policymaking, but also to increase the public's engagement towards sustainable futures that are attainable.

Introduction

The successful adoption of Beyond GDP (BGDP) metrics and their integration in policymaking hinge on how well these measures resonate with the public. Popular legitimacy is a critical factor in determining the political feasibility of BGDP adoption. When policymakers see these measures as reflective of societal values, it increases the likelihood of their integration into policymaking and evaluation processes at various governance levels. Moreover, governments that assess progress based on what matters most to people can gain a more comprehensive understanding of their performance and insights into how citizens will evaluate their mandate at the next electoral cycle.

To advance this goal, this brief presents novel data on the European public's views on Beyond GDP indicators. By polling nationally representative samples of six European Union (EU) countries —namely Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland and Spain— our findings ensure a broad geographic and demographic representation, reflecting the opinion of two-thirds of the EU population (67%).

The contribution of this policy brief is four-fold:

- i) It assesses overall support for a broader use of these indicators by national governments, to measure their countries' performance and to guide policy objectives.
- ii) It tests different communication strategies that promote these indicators' overall appeal.
- iii) It reveals preferences for these indicators' contents in terms of conceptual dimensions and themes covered (thematic domains).
- iv) It presents perceptions on and preferences for alternative visions of how a sustainable, carbon-neutral Europe could look like by 2050.

These findings provide key insights to EU and national level policymakers on the political feasibility of BGDP indicators in terms of their popular legitimacy. By understanding public preferences and possibilities for enhancing the appeal of BGDP indicators, this policy brief highlights evidence-based recommendations to foster buy-in of BGDP metrics; highlighting BGDP measures that are aligned with public sentiment; and increasing the likelihood of their adoption at national and EU levels.

Methods

The **selection of the six countries** to be surveyed was made based on several criteria including geographical coverage of different EU areas, population size as share of the EU total and political weight within the EU. The resulting selection includes the countries that satisfied the highest number of criteria and covers all four areas of the United Nations Geoscheme for Europe.

The **questionnaire was developed** in consultation with various experts from MERGE partners through an iterative design process, which also included pre-tests with small population samples to increase and ensure comprehension of the questions to laypersons. In adherence to GDPR law, all data were collected pseudonymously, and participation was voluntary. The survey received approval from Gent University's Ethical Committee within the Faculty of Economics and Business and it was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework platform in October 2024.

The **questionnaire was distributed** by the panel provider Bilendi Belgium. Fieldwork took place between October 26 and November 4, 2024. Average survey completion time varied across countries, ranging between 10 and 13 minutes.

Country samples were designed to be nationally representative, reflecting country-level statistics on age and gender (combined) as well as the educational level. The final sample selection was based on qualitative checks that excluded participants who failed attention and speed controls, leading to six final country samples of 1,000 participants each.

Four Key Results

1. Over 80% of European citizens support Beyond GDP indicators

European citizens overwhelmingly support the use of Beyond GDP (BGDP) indicators by their governments to measure national progress and guide policy. This survey, the first of its kind in Europe to assess both self-reported and observed preferences, reveals strong public backing for moving beyond GDP metrics, emphasizing a need for (additional) indicators on personal wellbeing, social, and environmental factors.

Across six European countries, 81% of respondents support using BGDP indicators to some extent (Figure 1):

- 17% favour BGDP metrics but prioritize GDP.

- 39% view BGDG indicators as equally important as GDP.
- 20% believe BGDG should have greater importance than GDP.
- 5% suggest BGDG metrics should fully replace GDP.

Support for BGDG indicators varies by country, ranging from 88% in Finland to 72% in Germany.

Figure 1. Self-reported support for Beyond GDP indicators

Notes: In this question BGDG metrics were formulated as personal wellbeing, social and environmental statistics.

The type of indicators that citizens want their countries to use as a measure of progress also reflects the type of economy Europeans want. Notably, 72% of respondents believe their economy should prioritize people’s and nature’s wellbeing over profits, indicating strong alignment with the principles of a wellbeing economy¹. This question was initially included in the Earth for All Global survey of 2024, which found that 68% of people living in the G20 countries supported a wellbeing economy in their country (Earth4All, 2024). In this sense, our results show that in Europe there is even a stronger popular constituency supporting the wellbeing economy than the global average.

¹ The question polled agreement with this statement “The economy of my country should prioritise the health and wellbeing of people and nature rather than focusing solely on profit and increasing incomes in the country”.

To validate these self-reported preferences, two real-stakes questions assessed respondents' willingness to act:

- **Petition Support:** On average, 77% of participants agreed to sign a petition urging their government to prioritize BGDG indicators in guiding policy objectives, with country-specific support ranging from 83% in Finland to 70% in France².
- **Donations to BGDG Advocacy:** When asked if they would donate part of a potential €100 prize win for participating to the survey, to a nonprofit advocating BGDG, 82% of respondents agreed, with an average donation of €24. Respondents committing to donate ranged from 91% in Italy to 74% in Finland.

Figure 2. General support for Beyond GDP indicators 2007-2024 (Germany, France, Italy)

Notes: Data for 2007, 2010, 2013, and 2020 is sourced from a longitudinal survey commissioned by Ethical Markets and conducted by GlobeScan. The survey excluded Italy from its last two rounds. Data for 2024 is derived from our own survey, using the same dataset presented in Figure 1 but focusing only on answers from respondents in a Control group (who received the same information about GDP as in the GlobeScan survey, as detailed in the next section).

The high proportion of individuals willing to support the BGDG agenda, either by signing a petition or making a monetary donation, reinforces our earlier finding that support for BGDG

² The petition text read: "I agree that it is essential for my country to broaden the use of personal wellbeing, social and environmental statistics. These statistics should play a central role in guiding government policy objectives. A society that values the wellbeing of both current and future generations cannot rely solely on an economic system focused on Gross Domestic Product (GDP)."

indicators is strong among Europeans. A significant majority is prepared to undergo a personal commitment, even in monetary terms, to advocate for this cause. Overall, the average level of support for BGDG measures appears consistent across the four measurements.

Stability of Support Over Time

Longitudinal comparisons with data from GlobeScan (2007–2020) show consistent support for BGDG metrics in France and Italy, averaging 75% and 84%, respectively (Figure 2). In Germany, support has fluctuated but remains strong, averaging 72% (GlobeScan, 2007, 2010, 2013, 2020)³. Global events, such as the Great Recession and the COVID-19 pandemic, may explain periodic surges in support as these crises expose the limitations of GDP-focused economies.

2. Support for Beyond GDP indicators could be enhanced even further through targeted communication

Effective communication strategies highlighting the limitations of GDP and emphasizing Beyond GDP (BGDP) indicators can bolster public support. This survey explored whether targeted messages focusing on wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability could influence preferences for BGDG measures.

Respondents were divided into five groups, each receiving distinct information about GDP and its limitations:

1. **Control Group:** basic definition of GDP and its uses.
2. **Wellbeing Treatment (T1):** added information on GDP's inability to measure wellbeing and quality of life.
3. **Inclusion Treatment (T2):** highlighted GDP's failure to capture inequalities.
4. **Sustainability Treatment (T3):** focused on GDP's omission of environmental costs.

³ Our question closely mirrors GlobeScan's, with two differences. First, GlobeScan provided only two response options—whether governments should continue using GDP alone or also adopt BGDG metrics. In contrast, our question expanded the second option to include four additional responses, which we consolidated into a single category in this graph for the purpose of comparison. Second, the GlobeScan survey described BGDG metrics as "health, social and environmental statistics", whereas our survey described them as "personal wellbeing, social and environmental statistics".

5. **Comprehensive Treatment (T4):** combined all three limitations.

Results showed that the **Inclusion Treatment (T2)** had a positive and statistically significant impact on general support for BGD, increasing average support on a 1–5 scale compared to the control group. However, the treatments showed no statistically significant effects on additional outcome variables, such as willingness to sign petitions or make donations.

Determinants of Support

Regression analysis identified additional key factors influencing support for BGD indicators:

- **Pre-existing Knowledge:** Respondents already familiar with BGD concepts were more likely to support these indicators.
- **Beliefs about Economic Growth:** Individuals who believed that the pursuit of economic growth strongly influences policy were more supportive of BGD measures.
- **Demographic Factors:** Women, younger people and those dissatisfied with their lives showed stronger support; whereas older individuals, right-wing voters, and higher-income respondents were less supportive.

Interactions Between Information and Demographics

Further analysis revealed nuanced interactions between information treatments and socio-demographic characteristics:

- **Income and Wellbeing Focus (T1):** Higher-income individuals responded positively to messages emphasizing quality of life.
- **Education and Inclusion Focus (T2):** Highly educated individuals were less responsive to messages framed around equality and inclusion.

3. The measures that matter: what types of Beyond GDP indicators do EU citizens want

Policymakers and researchers in the field identify growing public acceptance as the most significant driver for shifting beyond growth in policymaking (Hirvilammi et al., 2024). Consequently, after assessing overall public support for the BGD approach, it is essential to identify the indicators that best align with the priorities and values of European citizens.

In this survey, we draw on the identification of three key conceptual dimensions for measuring wellbeing: wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability, otherwise referred to as sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (Jansen et al., 2024). These dimensions, which initially emerged in the Stiglitz-Stern-Fitoussi report (Stiglitz et al., 2009), are increasingly gaining international consensus in the BGDG context. This is evidenced by recent global initiatives that have adopted these dimensions —such as the OECD Wellbeing framework and the European Commission report on Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (European Commission, 2024)— as well as a recent policy paper for the European Commission co-authored by experts from Horizon Europe projects SPES, ToBE, WISE, WISER, and MERGE (Hoekstra et al., 2024).

We find that European citizens strongly support BGDG measures that encompass the three dimensions of Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (Figure 3). Approximately three-fourths of respondents agree that their government should track these dimensions to measure the country's progress. Among them, sustainability received the highest level of support (77%), while inclusion had the lowest (72%). When interpolating individual level answers to these questions, we find that most citizens (60%) prefer indicators addressing all three dimensions, aligning with expert frameworks like the Stiglitz-Stern-Fitoussi report and recent EU initiatives.

Figure 3. Public support for Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing

We separately assessed preferences for the potential trade-off between the wellbeing of current and future generations: **85% of respondents valued the wellbeing of future generations as equally or more important to the wellbeing of current generations**(Figure

4). This finding highlights the public readiness to endorse policies balancing intergenerational equity.

Figure 4. Public preferences on intergenerational trade-offs

BGDP metrics encompass a wide array of themes, ranging from air quality to life expectancy at birth and the availability of free time. **Respondents identified health, safety, jobs, education, and housing as the top five thematic domains for inclusion in BGDP dashboards (Figure 5).**

Figure 5. Ranking of Beyond GDP thematic domains based on popular preferences

These preferences partly align with findings from similar datasets, such as user preferences collected by the OECD Better Life Index (p.46, Charveriat et al., 2024), but they may nonetheless be exposed to contextual sensitivity. Recent geopolitical tensions and rising inflation appear to have heightened concerns about safety and economic stability. Evidence from a recent Eurobarometer survey highlights this shift, revealing that climate change, which was Europeans' top concern in 2021, had fallen to third place by 2023, ranking behind poverty and armed conflicts (Eurobarometer, 2023). This contextual sensitivity should be taken into account when interpreting public preferences.

In addition, **respondents expressed preferences in terms of** technical characteristics of BGDPI Indicators:

- **Cross-Country Comparability vs. Country-Specific Indicators:** two-thirds of respondents favored dashboards that equally incorporate country-specific and universal indicators, reinforcing the need for a set of country-specific indicators that reflect a nation's cultural values or developmental stage⁴.
- **Objective vs. Subjective Measurements:** a majority (75%) supported either equal weight or a stronger emphasis on objective indicators.

4. People's visions of a sustainable future depend on what they consider attainable

In the final part of the questionnaire, we asked participants to imagine and evaluate alternative visions of what a sustainable, carbon-neutral Europe would look like by the year 2050. Living well within environmental limits can take different forms, and preferences for each of them may depend on societal and individual level values and beliefs (EEA, 2024). By asking how each of these visions of the future resonates with EU citizens, we indirectly sought to understand the qualities they associate with an ideal society (Kraftt et al. 2013). These insights can inform the design and implementation of policies necessary to realize these visions in the years ahead. Using four distinct scenarios developed by the European Environment Agency (EEA), we examined public preferences, perceived feasibility, and key determinants of support. This is the first time that public preferences for alternative future scenarios have been elicited at the European level.

⁴ Given the complexity of the question, we enabled respondents to indicate whether they did not understand or had no clear preferences, 14% of respondents chose this option.

Participants evaluated four scenarios depicting different pathways towards a carbon neutral Europe. These scenarios were simplified to focus on three critical dimensions⁵:

- **Main avenue to stay within planetary boundaries:** each scenario explores different ways the economy can reorganize to respect the planet's ecological limits, including technological breakthroughs or changes in the behaviour of citizens and businesses, which can be either voluntary or enforced through regulatory mechanisms and incentives.
- **Governance model:** The relative involvement of national governments, EU institutions, the free market, or local communities in organizing the economy.
- **Relationship to Economic Growth:** Perspectives on GDP, ranging from continuous growth to degrowth or neutrality to GDP.

Summary of the four scenarios

Technocracy for the Common Good: Strict regulations and taxes drive resource efficiency. National governments play a larger role in managing economies. GDP grows, mostly driven by consumption of greener products.

Unity in Adversity: EU institutions have a more central role in economic governance, enforcing sustainability through taxes and regulations. Economic growth is no longer a priority.

Green Growth⁶: Technological breakthroughs boost resource efficiency. The free market plays a greater role in guiding the economy, while GDP grows steadily.

Ecotopia: Voluntary lifestyle shifts toward simplicity ensure planetary boundaries are respected. Local communities gain more direct control over the economy, while economic activity declines.

Technocracy for the Common Good and *Green Growth* emerged as the scenarios deemed most likely to materialize (Figure 6), with 41% of respondents rating them as either extremely or somewhat probable. In contrast, *Ecotopia* faced significant scepticism, as 41% considered it unlikely to occur.

⁵ Given the time constraints related to the questionnaire's length, it was necessary to first synthesize and then standardize the original scenarios descriptions to emphasize the key features that set them apart from one another.

⁶ Green Growth was renamed from its original title "The great decoupling" to make its meaning more immediately clear and accessible to the public.

Figure 6. Public probability perceptions on sustainable futures for Europe in 2050

In terms of desirability, *Green Growth* garnered the highest support, with 62% of participants finding it appealing (Figure 7). *Ecotopia* and *Technocracy for the Common Good* followed closely, each being rated as desirable by 55% of respondents. *Unity in Adversity* received the lowest level of endorsement, with 51% viewing it as desirable.

Figure 7. Public preferences for sustainable futures for Europe in 2050

Econometric analysis show that preferences for the scenarios were influenced by several key factors. The most consistent finding across scenarios is the strong positive relationship between their perceived likelihood and their desirability. Respondents who view a scenario as more likely to happen tend to rate it as more desirable. This suggests that **expectations about a scenario’s feasibility heavily influence its appeal, highlighting the importance of ensuring these expectations are realistic.** For example, individuals who see *Green Growth* as a plausible future may overestimate the feasibility of achieving absolute decoupling between economic activity and resource use or emissions—an assumption that many expert reviews contest given the narrowing time window to prevent surpassing critical climate tipping points (Haberl et al., 2020). On the other hand, *Ecotopia* is the second most desirable

scenario despite it being perceived as the least likely to occur, possibly reflecting not the lack of support for such an idea but an understanding that it is unlikely to be met with political will. Public scepticism about *Ecotopia's* feasibility suggests the need for clear communication and strategies to address perceived political and logistical challenges.

Beliefs about the role of GDP also played a significant part; participants who perceived GDP as having a strong impact on government decisions were more likely to favour *Ecotopia* and showed less inclination toward *Technocracy for the Common Good* or *Unity in Adversity*.

Recommendations for a citizens' backed implementation of Beyond GDP

1. Align indicators with citizen priorities

- **Adopt a Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing Framework:** Citizens endorse this conceptual approach to measuring societal progress, as testified by the high approval rates that each of these three conceptual dimensions gained. Consequently, the BGDP indicators selected should cover these three dimensions either simultaneously (indexes) or consist of an indicator set that comprises indicators for each dimension separately.
- **Focus on salient topics:** BGDP measures should include domains that citizens identify as critical to progress, including amongst others health, safety, jobs, education, and housing. These indicators align closely with public preferences and can serve as a foundation for broader acceptance.
- **Highlight intergenerational trade-offs within policy:** 85% of respondents value future generations' wellbeing equally or more than theirs. As such, emphasizing the long-term benefits for future generations as the reason for present-day sacrifices may increase public support for policies involving trade-offs between current and future generations' wellbeing. Moreover, this challenges the "status quo" in policymaking, which tends to prioritize the interests of current generations.
- **Balance the composition of a global measurement framework:** beyond experts' opinion, public opinion should be considered in the design of a homogenous global measurement framework for BGDP measures. The public endorses the inclusion of country-specific indicators and a consistent if not predominant share of objectively measured indicators.

2. Leverage public awareness and build knowledge

- **Increase education on BGDG indicators:** Pre-existing awareness of BGDG metrics correlates with higher support. Similarly, individuals who believe that GDP significantly influences policymaking are more likely to support BGDG measures. Governments and organizations should invest in public education programs and campaigns to increase understanding of how alternative measures to GDP reflect societal progress and to highlighting the pivotal role that GDP currently has in shaping policy decisions.

3. Tailor communication strategies for diverse audiences

- **Emphasize inclusion:** Highlighting the inclusivity of BGDG indicators has proven to significantly increase overall public support. Messaging should underscore the role of these measures in promoting equality and improving quality of life for all citizens.
- **Tailor communication strategies to engage diverse audiences:** Communication campaigns should be customized to address the varying levels of support for BGDG initiatives across different socio-demographic groups. While women, younger individuals, those dissatisfied with their lives, and lower-income populations tend to show stronger support, efforts must also target older, conservative, and higher-income individuals who are less favorable towards BGDG measures. Messaging should be adaptable, as the inclusion dimension generally resonates well, but may be less effective for higher-educated individuals. For higher-income groups, emphasizing the personal wellbeing and quality of life improvements associated with BGDG can significantly enhance support.

4. Mind the gap between public expectations and policy feasibility

- **Highlight realistic scenarios:** Public support for alternative visions for the future is closely tied to their perceived feasibility. Policymakers should present scenarios that are considered attainable based on the most updated scientific evidence to avoid misleading the public into visions that have limited chances to materialize (e.g. consider whether there is clear evidence of sufficient absolute decoupling between economic activity and resource use to propose the pursuit of a green growth scenario).

- **Address feasibility concerns:** Policymakers must transparently address potential challenges and communicate pathways to achieving proposed goals, by presenting the implications and societal trade-offs of pursuing a given vision of the future in a clear and accessible manner (e.g. highlight the consequences on equality of pursuing green growth, or the changes required to make the functioning of the State less dependent on economic growth).

Integrating BGDG measures into decision-making processes offers a transformative opportunity to redefine societal progress. While the final choice of BGDG metrics or of a global measurement framework critically depends on experts' knowledge, attention to public preferences will be essential to ensure public support and engagement. By aligning indicators with public sentiment, employing inclusive communication strategies, and addressing feasibility concerns, European policymakers can build a robust foundation for adopting BGDG frameworks.

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